

AMERICAN-STYLE SECRET "SKULDUGGERY" FATAL FLAWS OF "NARXCARE®"
-- WHAT MARK TWAIN WOULD SAY ABOUT PREDICTIVE MEDICINENeil Anand MD¹, Mark Ibsen MD², Richard A. Lawhern PhD^{3*}

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ABSTRACT

Background: In this paper, the authors set forth in prose readable by clinical non-professionals, several fundamental reasons for deep caution in applying NarxCare ® or any other algorithm based on artificial intelligence to the practice of pain medicine. **Objectives:** To assess the dangers and fallacies in use of the NarxCare instrument as a pre-filter for patient access to safe and effective pain care employing prescription opioid analgesics. **Methods:** Critical review of the clinical literature on pain and addiction. **Findings:** AI-based algorithms like NarxCare simply do not apply to individuals and are incapable of incorporating individual nuances. No competent clinician would ever plan a course of pain management without extensive patient workup and individualized treatment. NarxCare as presently applied actively suppresses individualized care by potentially criminalizing clinician decisions.

DISCUSSION

A proprietary patient profiling instrument called "NarxCare" is now in wide use by US State Prescription Drug Management Programs.^[4] This proprietary product of Bamboo Health is represented as "a set of data and tools that are intended to support a healthcare provider's review of a patient's controlled substance data from government-managed and regulated Prescription Drug Monitoring Programs (PDMPs)."

However, several papers and sources have criticized NarxCare methods or findings, highlighting concerns around risk scoring, patient discrimination, and clinical impacts:

- A law review article^[5] critiques NarxCare for using problematic risk indicators such as criminal history, payment method, and travel distance, which may discriminate against marginalized populations and lead to inappropriate clinical decisions like forced medication tapering or treatment denial. The paper raises skepticism about the clinical validity of NarxCare's risk scores and their regulatory implications, suggesting that NarxCare may exacerbate discrimination against patients with complex medical needs.
- Another published perspective^[6] addresses concerns about the transparency of NarxCare's proprietary algorithms and false positive/negative risk classifications. The authors emphasize that NarxCare should be used as a screening tool rather than a definitive diagnostic measure, while

defending its utility in reducing manual screening burdens, but acknowledging limitations in specificity.

- Research^[7] has also linked high NarxCare scores with certain adverse postoperative outcomes, underscoring the score's association with risk but also pointing to possible limitations in predicting clinical events. Moreover, the authors note that "effect sizes are so small that the finding is unlikely to be clinically meaningful."

Mark Twain (Samuel Clemens) spent his youth deciphering the Mississippi River, a system far more complex than any artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm. He learned that real understanding demands nuance, context, and skepticism. Were he alive today, he'd likely see NarxCare as a cautionary tale about the dangers of replacing human judgment with "lies, damn lies, and statistics."

NarxCare scores patients based on factors in their history. These include morphine milligram equivalents and pharmacy shopping patterns. Critical factors are ignored, such as tolerance, genetics, and socioeconomic context -- factors that Twain, the great observer of human complexity, never overlooked. Like river pilots who mistook calm waters for safety, NarxCare's designers seem to have believed that prescription data can predict overdose risk with mathematical certainty. But Twain knew better: beneath calm surfaces often lurk deadly currents.

Samuel Clemens' romantic view of the river faded as he learned its hidden mechanics. In river slang, "Mark Twain" meant "two fathoms deep", a safe depth for steamboats to navigate, measured by the leadsmen's line and called out to the pilot as a signal of safe passage through uncertain waters. Similarly, AI strips medicine of nuance, reducing pain care to a combined risk score. Patients stable for years on medication are flagged as "high-risk" for crossing arbitrary AI algorithm thresholds. Like a pilot misreading a river chart, AI can't distinguish danger from routine -- a failure of judgment Twain would have derided.

"There are three kinds of lies: lies, damned lies, and statistics," Twain once quipped.^[8] NarxCare inherits the biases in its data^[9], much like AI predictive policing that conflates over-policing with high crime. In fact, AI-based algorithms can hallucinate due to biases in the data they access. Hallucination in AI refers to the generation of false or misleading information presented as fact. This phenomenon occurs when AI models produce outputs that are not accurate or are fabricated, often confidently delivered as true.

A very strong case can be made that almost the entirety of the clinical literature and US public health policy pertaining to pain management and addiction fit the description immediately above.^{[10], [11], [12]}

In some communities, higher prescription rates reflect access or need -- but NarxCare interprets incidence as risk. Twain, who distrusted blind consensus, would have seen this as statistical tyranny. Modern clinicians should be like minded.

And then there's the human cost.

Twain's characters—Huck, Jim, the Duke and King—were messy, flawed, and human. Artificial intelligence reduces people to categories. A chronic pain patient becomes a red flag. A veteran is labeled "likely to misuse." A trauma survivor is deemed ineligible for relief. Real people are harmed. Doctors retreat into defensive medicine. Patients lose care.

Despair follows

Twain understood that mechanical systems, no matter how sophisticated, cannot replace human experience and wisdom. Artificial intelligence, like the shifting sandbars of the Mississippi, offers the illusion of control while concealing danger. Twain would warn us, not only because prediction is useless, but because blind faith in flawed AI models is perilous. As is often attributed to Twain or humorist Will Rogers, "It ain't what you don't know that gets you into trouble. It's what you know for sure that just ain't so."

Despite all its data, NarxCare AI knows far less than it claims. Twain once read the river like a book, each ripple a word, each eddy a phrase. That living water shaped his

vision of America. Today, our rivers are streams and waves of anonymized data, cold and unfeeling, feeding systems like NarxCare and AI predictive policing. These promise clarity but often deliver distortion. If Twain read rivers to understand America, then we must learn to read these digital currents and waves with equal care.

Twain's life depended on tiny observations, a flicker in the current, a shadow on the water. AI mimics this vigilance but without understanding. AI watches everything and knows nothing. Its judgments are indifferent and often erroneous. It lacks the reflexes and humanity of a pilot who knew life and death depended on subtle clues.

As Twain mastered the river, he mourned the magic lost to mechanistic understanding. In "Life on the Mississippi"^[13], he lamented how poetry gave way to measurement. Today, we too have traded reality for red flag metrics. NarxCare AI reduces human pain relief to a number and clinician care to a patient data entry. It replaces doctor-patient relationships with AI black-box decisions. Patterns become pathology. Nuance is overridden by numbers. We're left with "Garbage In, Garbage Out," disguised as AI and run by technocrats who've never left the river dock.

We've traded poetry for computer code and in the process, lost compassion, creativity, and the courage to see patients as individual people.

Twain's river teemed with unpredictable, complex lives. That chaos gave his writing a soul. Today's AI algorithms offer no such complexity. A mother in pain becomes a liability. A veteran becomes a statistic. A survivor becomes suspect.

This isn't help — it's harm. And who benefits? Certainly not patients.

No competent doctor would decide upon a course of treatment for an individual, without first doing a detailed workup and history assessment *for that individual*. AI-based algorithms like NarxCare simply do not apply to individuals and are incapable of incorporating individual nuances. Worse, these algorithms now incorporate hidden assumptions that are deeply contradicted by well-established science:

- According to no less authority than Nora Volkow, MD, Director of the National Institute on Drug Abuse, "Unlike tolerance and physical dependence, addiction is not a predictable result of opioid prescribing. Addiction occurs in only a small percentage of persons who are exposed to opioids — even among those with preexisting vulnerabilities. Older medical texts and several versions of the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM) either overemphasized the role of tolerance and physical dependence in the definition of addiction or equated these processes (DSM-III

and DSM-IV). However, more recent studies have shown that the molecular mechanisms underlying addiction are distinct from those responsible for tolerance and physical dependence, in that they evolve much more slowly, last much longer, and disrupt multiple brain processes.”^[14]

- It is also known that rates of opioid analgesic prescribing by doctors to their patients have no relationship *of any kind* to either (a) rates of hospital admissions for opioid toxicity, or (b) rates of accidental death involving prescription opioids.^[15]
^[16] These facts are confirmed and referenced in the 2023 consensus guidelines of the American Association of Interventional Pain Physicians.^[17]

Twain knew freedom involves risk, but the rich human tapestry he celebrated is too often these days flattened into spreadsheets. These systems erase complexity rather than reflect it. Huck and Jim found freedom on the river, but only by respecting its dangers and learning its rhythms. Our digital systems should do the same. NarxCare claims to protect but often punishes. People lose care not because of wrongdoing, but because an AI algorithm labels them as a threat to doctors who treat them or pharmacists who fill their prescriptions.

There is no appeal. No raft. No Huck Finn to escape with.

Freedom in the digital age demands more than computer code. It demands transparency, humility, and safeguards against AI algorithmic violence. Twain warned: “Whenever you find yourself on the side of the majority, it is time to pause and reflect.” AI algorithms speak in a language few understand, but many obey. They are maps handed to children expected to pilot ships. Designed by the powerful, enforced on the powerless, NarxCare, like AI predictive policing, wears the mask of objectivity while reproducing old injustices. It doesn’t see people. It sees probabilities. It acts not on what someone has done, but what a machine predicts they might do. NarxCare replaces care with control.

In Twain’s era, the steamboat symbolized progress. But Twain wasn’t seduced. He was no Connecticut Yankee. He knew technology without judgment was dangerous. The river was alive. It required respect. Misreading it was fatal. AI is our generation’s new steamboat — praised for efficiency, yet blind to nuance. Twain would have seen through it. He would have recognized the hubris in believing machines can replace wisdom. Heraclitus said, “You cannot step into the same river twice.” AI disagrees. It treats people as static patterns, denying change and redemption.

We must resist this flattening. Real rivers and real people don’t move in straight lines. Twain’s river carried rogues and saints, all sharing the same current. He knew freedom came with risk, and compassion required

understanding. Twain’s river taught him to read America, its beauty, blindness, and contradictions. Our modern data streams could do the same, but only if we approach them with Twain’s skeptical eye.

We must ask ourselves.

- Who built these AI systems?
- Whose stories are excluded?
- What truths are erased?
- What myths are sold as science?

Twain wrote, “The face of the water, in time, became a wonderful book.” Today, the face of AI has become a dangerous fiction. Each metric is a mask, each score a potential death sentence. If we don’t learn to read these scores wisely, we risk losing not just justice but the practice of medicine itself.

CONCLUSIONS

Both the clinical literature and simple common sense support the immediate suspension of reliance upon NarxCare® as a predictor of outcomes in individual patients, rendered in advance of treatment and ongoing management of either chronic pain or addiction. Denial of the most effective (and one of the safest) classes of pharmaceutical pain management on the basis of this tool should be regarded as medical malpractice and healthcare fraud.

At most, this tool may be useful for some patients, their healthcare providers and their pharmacists, a part of the time, in flagging individuals who may need additional support and more frequent monitoring of outcomes.

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